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DAMATH Integration in Teaching Mathematics: Inputs on Teaching Styles

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to determine the efficacy of DAMATH Integration in the mathematics instructions of the Grade 7 teachers in teaching integers in a public secondary school. It aimed to analyze if there is a significant relationship between application and use of DAMATH in teaching mathematics. This study utilized various methods including percentages, weighted mean, K-12 level of proficiency, DepEd K-12 transmuted grade, Pearson rank-order correlation coefficient, and paired-samples t-test for data analysis. After thorough analysis, it has been determined that the integration of the DAMATH game in mathematics instruction yields a significant impact on students' comprehensive understanding of mathematical concepts, particularly in the realm of integers. Consequently, a program named (AIMED) Advancing Integration through a Multidimensional Educational Approach in DAMATH is proposed for the benefit of teachers and learners. Furthermore, the study implies that applying a DAMATH board game in teaching mathematics is effective to improve students' performance in learning integers. However, the research limitations include not exploring potential challenges or drawbacks of using DAMATH, and the study is solely focused on Grade 7 students and mathematics teachers. Lastly, the implementation of DAMATH in online learning platforms is suggested for ensuring continuity, but practical implications and potential challenges of this adaptation are not discussed in detail.

Keywords: *board games, DAMATH integration, mathematics instruction, online learning platform*

Introduction

The integration of educational games into teaching practices has gained significant attention globally as educators seek innovative approaches to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes (Bouchrika et al., 2021; Lamb et al., 2018). In the Philippines, where there is a continuous effort to improve mathematics education, the adoption of games like DAMATH has emerged as a potential strategy (Tomines et al., 2021). Integrating DAMATH in teaching is an educational game that combines mathematics with the idea of a local strategic game called dama by including computational values on its chips (Ramos et al., 2011). DAMATH, with its blend of mathematical concepts and recreational gameplay, presents an opportunity to make learning mathematics more enjoyable and effective. However, the success of integrating DAMATH into teaching mathematics depends greatly on the teaching styles employed by educators. Understanding how different teaching styles interact with DAMATH gameplay can provide valuable insights into optimizing its educational benefits. Hence, exploring the inputs on teaching styles in DAMATH integration becomes imperative in both the global discourse on educational game integration and the context of mathematics education in the Philippines.

DAMATH game has been marketed in the Philippines as a collaborative endeavor to raise awareness of learning mathematics, particularly among students. It integrates local culture, education, and technology to make mathematics teaching and learning more enjoyable, tricky, and interactive for students. By giving Filipino students competitive life-long learning opportunities for comprehension and ICT-fluency skills, the DAMATH board game ushers them into the new millennium in its distinctive way (Huenda, 2010). Students learn to investigate, solidify, deepen, and apply the concepts of real numbers and their properties and operations to everyday tasks by playing the board game DAMATH. However, the success of integrating DAMATH into teaching mathematics depends significantly on the teaching styles employed by educators. Understanding how different teaching styles interact with DAMATH gameplay can provide valuable insights into optimizing its educational benefits. Hence, exploring the inputs on teaching styles in DAMATH integration becomes imperative in both the global discourse on educational game integration and the context of mathematics education in the Philippines.

Several authors have explored the integration of educational games, including DAMATH, into mathematics teaching. For instance, Ramirez and Mercado (2023) found that incorporating mathematical games into the classroom can improve students' understanding of basic operations on integers and rational numbers, increase their mathematics achievement scores, enhance their learning experiences, and improve their achievement in the subject. Similarly, Aluan (2018) found that game-based learning effectively improved mathematical performance among pupils. This suggests that incorporating games into the classroom can effectively enhance student achievement in mathematics, particularly in motivating learners to grasp mathematical concepts. Furthermore, Armayan (2019) conducted a program that aimed to improve students' mastery level in performing integer operations. The program focused on enhancing students' skills in integer operations to boost their mathematical proficiency and understanding in this fundamental area of mathematics.

Despite the existing studies on DAMATH integration in teaching mathematics, there still needs to be more knowledge regarding the efficacy of DAMATH integration in mathematics instructions. While some studies have touched upon the topic, there needs to be a

more comprehensive analysis that systematically examines the significant relationship between the Application and Use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics. To address the identified gap in knowledge, this study determines the efficacy of DAMATH Integration in the mathematics instructions of the Grade 7 teachers in teaching integers. It aimed to know if a significant relationship exists between the application and use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the efficacy of DAMATH Integration in the mathematics instructions of the Grade 7 teachers in teaching integers in a public secondary school. It aimed to analyze if there is a significant relationship between the application and use of DAMATH in teaching mathematics.

Literature Review

DAMATH Integration

Educational gaming is the use of games in educational contexts to achieve educational objectives (De Freitas et al., 2018). It is a pedagogical method that combines traditional and digital games to promote and enhance learning, teaching, and evaluation. It boosts students' academic aptitude and cognitive ability, which leads to higher academic accomplishment (Byun & Loh, 2015). Game-based learning allows students to study more actively and enthusiastically (Hilliard & Kargbo, 2017). According to the study by Lane et al. (2022), it prepares students for future learning by imparting new knowledge and skills, practicing, reinforcing previously acquired knowledge and skills, and developing 21st-century skills. It also maintains students' interest and attention. Specialized education, enough practice, prompt feedback, and mentoring from rivals and friends will benefit the learner. The idea evolves naturally as the learners play the game since game-based learning parallels the lesson's contents. Additionally, the learner unknowingly picks up declarative and procedural knowledge.

Board games may be utilized to further explore learning and concepts like motivation and computational thinking in both formal and informal contexts since they simplify complicated problems and systems and can be used as a learning tool that has potential and is beneficial to the students. In the classroom, board games are frequently used (Noda et al., 2019). DAMATH has been the subject of various studies to assess its effectiveness in teaching mathematics concepts and enhancing students' understanding. A study by Ramirez and Mercado (2023) aimed to determine the impact of game-based learning on students' mathematical achievements. They found a significant association between the extent of utilizing GBA (Game-Based Activities) such as DAMATH for motivation, engagement, performance, and application, and various factors such as age, sex, teaching experience, and highest educational attainment. Çelik (2018) investigated the impact of activity-based learning on students' mathematical achievement and attitudes towards mathematics activities. The study found that activity-based learning significantly improved students' mathematical achievement and attitudes towards mathematics activities compared to traditional teaching methods. The study suggests that activity-based learning can be an effective teaching strategy to enhance students' mathematical achievement and attitudes towards mathematics activities.

Teaching Mathematics

Mathematics teaching is an essential field of education that has been the subject of extensive research and development in recent years (Kilpatrick, 2020). Hoyles (2018) delves into the interconnectedness between mathematical knowledge, pedagogy, and digital tools, emphasizing how these elements shape mathematical practices in teaching and learning. By exploring the transformative potential of digital technologies in mathematics education, the research highlights the importance of leveraging these tools to enhance conceptual engagement and foster a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts among learners and teachers. The use of primary sources in mathematics teaching has also been recognized as a valuable method for promoting an enriched understanding of the subject and its genesis and encouraging students to engage with the original problems from which concepts arose (White, 2015). Furthermore, integrating information literacy into mathematics classrooms effectively prepares students for the quantitative arguments they may encounter daily (Erickson, 2019). Therefore, mathematics teaching should be a dynamic and multifaceted process that incorporates a variety of teaching methods, technologies, and resources to support students' learning and understanding of mathematical concepts.

The study by Căprioară (2015) emphasized the significance of problem-solving in mathematics learning, as it provides a context for learning mathematical concepts and enables students to transfer their existing knowledge to unfamiliar situations. The research highlights the importance of problem-solving in mathematics education, allowing students to understand and explain the processes used to arrive at solutions rather than merely memorizing and applying a set of procedures. Savelsbergh et al. (2016) conducted a meta-analytic review to investigate the impact of innovative science and mathematics teaching on student attitudes and achievement. Their research synthesized the effects of innovative teaching methods in science and mathematics, shedding light on how these approaches influence student attitudes and academic performance in these subjects.

The study by Perera and John (2020) investigated the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs for teaching math and teacher and student outcomes. The study found that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs for teaching math were positively associated with teachers' job satisfaction, classroom interaction quality, and student math achievement. Additionally, individual perceptions of interaction quality and math self-concept were positively associated with math achievement at the student level. The study highlights the importance of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in shaping classroom processes and student outcomes and emphasizes the need for targeted

interventions to enhance teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in teaching math. Furthermore, Baier et al. (2019) delve into the relative importance of mathematics teachers' cognitive ability, personality, knowledge, beliefs, and motivation for instructional quality. Through a comprehensive investigation involving various teacher characteristics, the research sheds light on the significant predictors of instructional quality in mathematics teaching. Baier et al. (2019) found that extraversion, enthusiasm for teaching, and pedagogical/psychological knowledge were critical predictors of learning support, highlighting the intricate interplay between teacher attributes and instructional effectiveness in mathematics education.

Teaching Styles

Every learner has a different learning style, and it is not possible to significantly alter a learner's learning style. To fit the learning styles of their students, teachers should adapt their teaching methods. Just as every student has a different learning style, teachers have specific teaching methods that work best for them. Learning more about their classmates' various learning preferences can be quite beneficial for both teachers and students. (Stankovska et al., 2020). Roblon et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between teaching strategies and students' performance in mathematics. They found that the use of technology, collaboration, and problem-based learning strategies positively affected students' performance. The study suggests further research on the effectiveness of technology-based teaching strategies in mathematics education and the development of policies to ensure equitable access to technology for all students.

People study in many ways and use many different learning styles. However, lecturers might only sometimes deliver content and learning opportunities that suit their students' learning preferences. Students satisfied with their courses do well because of a mismatch between their learning and teaching styles (Chetty et al., 2019). Thus, teaching methods influence how well students perform overall during the learning process (Benedicto et al., 2023; Bonney, 2015; Geverola et al., 2024; Sivarajah et al., 2019). However, the absence of research into best matching the teaching and learning styles prevents the process from moving further. The effectiveness of instructional methods may be better than during implementation due to this gap. Thus, the key to a successful teaching process is matching the teaching methods to the students' learning preferences.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a single group, quasi-experimental design which offers a practical approach to studying the integration of DAMATH (an educational game) in teaching mathematics. Using quasi-experimental methods allows control over certain variables while observing real-world teaching environments (Price et al., 2015). This approach provides valuable insights into how the extent of DAMATH Board Games influences teaching styles and its potential benefits for mathematics teaching.

Participants

The study's respondents were mathematics teachers and grade 7 students in a public secondary school in Talisay City, Cebu, Philippines, with a total population of more than 891 students. Using cluster sampling, the respondents of this research were seven mathematics teachers and 30 grade 7 students. Seven female mathematics teachers, eighteen male students, ten female students, one LGBTQIA+ student, and one gender-neutral student. The student respondents came from the same section. They were the chosen respondents by the integration of DAMATH board games in teaching styles.

Cluster sampling is utilized in this study because it allows for the efficient selection of groups of respondents who share similar characteristics or contexts. In this case, the study focuses on mathematics teachers and grade 7 students. By selecting intact clusters of teachers and students from this school, the study can capture the unique dynamics of DAMATH integration within this educational setting. Additionally, cluster sampling enables the researchers to obtain a representative sample from the larger population of students in the school, ensuring that the findings are applicable to the broader context. This sampling is an essential method in statistics and market research due to its efficiency and cost-effectiveness. This method is particularly useful when dealing with a diverse population or when logistical complexities arise, as it simplifies data collection and allows for the capture of diversity within the population (Bhardwaj, 2019; Taherdoost, 2016).

Instruments

The research instruments used in this study include an adapted and modified questionnaire (for students) and a survey questionnaire (for mathematics teachers), which is an adapted, modified, and researchers-made survey. The adapted and modified questionnaire (for students) determined the age, sex, and socio-economic status of student respondents. The adapted and modified questionnaire (for students) was derived from DepEd modules containing a test from basic mathematical operations (e.g., addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division) to determine the pre-test and post-test scores. The adapted and modified questionnaire (for students) has four (4) parts, which all contain 10-item multiple choice of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. This both applies to the pre-test and post-test of the student respondents. Meanwhile, the survey questionnaire (for mathematics teachers) determined the age, sex, civil status, number of years teaching mathematics in Grade 7, length of service in teaching, and training/seminars/workshops on DAMATH Games of Teacher respondents. The survey questionnaire (for mathematics teachers) highlights teachers' conceptual understanding of the core knowledge, procedural fluency, adaptive reasoning, productive disposition, presence, and use of DAMATH

in teaching. The survey questionnaire (for mathematics teachers) was derived from the research paper of Al-Mutawah et al. (2019), and it served as a primary source of the components of the survey questionnaire. In terms of validity, the adapted and modified questionnaire (for students) and the survey questionnaire (for mathematics teachers) used face validity and content validity to ensure the efficacy of both questionnaires. The validation process was conducted by experts in instrumentation in the institute, with the evaluators' comments and suggestions integrated into the final draft. Furthermore, the study used a split-half method for the reliability of the two survey questionnaires, and it got a reliability rating through Cronbach Alpha of 0.957, which indicated that the two survey questionnaires were excellent. Moreover, the study used the 4-point Likert scale to measure the perceptions of Grade 7 mathematics teachers in integrating DAMATH board games in teaching mathematics.

Procedure

The data gathering of the study started with the formulation of the research hypothesis and objectives. Then selecting respondents and survey questionnaires making. An approval letter was sought from the principal before conducting the study with the selected Grade 7 students and teachers. Upon approval, the researchers retrieved the consent letters. The researchers also asked permission from the mathematics teacher to provide their demographic profile through the completion of the survey questionnaire and for the researcher to secure the permanent records of the respondents. Then, pretest was employed pretest to gauge students' proficiency in the four fundamental arithmetic operations, followed by the implementation of DAMATH as an intervention or activity. Respondents were adequately informed about the DAMATH board game before they were set to take part in a test. Each mechanic of DAMATH was explained thoroughly for further understanding. After the intervention, a posttest was given to the students. The researchers collected the complete form and test questionnaire and then tabulated, analyzed, and arranged the data and information gathered from their respondents.

Data Analysis

Frequency and percentage were used to determine the profile of the teachers and students in order to analyze the data obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the application and use of DAMATH in teaching mathematics. K-12 level of proficiency, DepEd K-12 transmuted grades were used to analyze the pretest and posttest performance of the students. Lastly, the Pearson rank-order correlation coefficient was used to determine the Significant Relationship between the application and use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics, and the paired-sample t-test was used to determine the Significant difference between the pretest and post-test performance of the students.

Results and Discussion

On the Profile of the Participants (Students)

Table 1 represents the data to answer the problem on the personal profile of the students-participants in terms of their age, gender, and combined family income. From the survey it was revealed that most of the students were aged 13-15 with twenty (20) respondents, eighteen (18) were male. From the survey, it was also revealed that twenty (20) have less than or equal to 10000 combined family income.

Table 1. Profile of the students

Profile		f	%
Age	10-12 years old	10	33.3
	13-15 years old	20	66.7
	16-18 years old	0	0.0
	19 years old and above	0	0.0
Gender	Male	18	60.0
	Female	10	33.3
	LGBTQIA+	1	3.3
	Rather not say	1	3.3
Combined Family Income (in peso)	Less than or equal to 10000	20	66.7
	10001-20000	2	6.7
	20001-30000	3	10.0
	30001-40000	1	3.3
	40001-50000	2	6.7
	More than 50000	2	6.7

This implies that the age of the respondents, most of the students are between the ages of 13-15 years old. Based on the general expectations set by the DepEd in the Philippines, the age range for incoming Grade 7 students is typically 12 to 14 years old. However, there may be some flexibility in the age range due to various factors such as late enrolments, repeating a grade, or other circumstances. As people grow older, their cognitive abilities, which are crucial for sustaining functional autonomy, such as acquiring new skills, tend to deteriorate. However, certain types of motor learning seem to remain intact with age, whereas learning tasks that necessitate associative binding tend to be adversely influenced (Clark, et al., 2015). The result also shows that most of the students in grade 7 are

male with 18 out of the 30 student-respondents. According to Ghazvini and Khajehpour (2011), no gender differences were observed in the external locus of control, academic self-concept, and study aids and test strategies. However, it was discovered that children have different cognitive-motivational approaches to learning tasks in academic settings, with girls having a more adaptable approach. Nonetheless, the study did not consider contextual variables that could have different impacts on boys' and girls' motivation. Moreover, when it comes to the combined family income. The result shows that most of the respondents have an income of less than or equal to 10,000 pesos per month. 10,000 pesos is the lowest category when it comes to the table. This concludes that the majority of the respondents have a low combined family income. Low family income is associated with poor academic achievement among children. Higher rates of school absence and tardiness may be one mechanism through which low family income impacts children's academic success. Poor attendance patterns predict poorer grades, with absences more associated with grades than tardiness. Results do not provide strong evidence that absences and tardiness meaningfully attenuate relations between the duration of low family income and student achievement; poorer attendance and persistent low income independently predict poorer grades (Morrissey et al., 2014).

The results reflect that a student's profile is very important for learning. Students need to know what the best age for a certain grade is because age greatly affects the cognitive skills of one's students. Student profiles provide valuable information for planning educational strategies and policies and improving faculty expertise on learning issues. Students' combined family income may also affect the student's grades and other academic achievements and limit their capabilities academically.

On the Profile of the Participants (Teachers)

Table 2 represents the data to answer the problem on the personal profile of the teacher-participants in terms of their age, gender, civil status, length of service in teaching, number of years in teaching mathematics in Grade 7, and relevant training/seminars/workshops on DAMATH games in mathematics teaching. From the survey, it was revealed that most of the mathematics teachers were aged 36-40 with four (4) respondents, seven (7) were female and four (4) were still married. From the survey, it was also revealed that the math teachers served 1-5 and 6-10 years in teaching with two (2) respondents each, five (5) respondents have 1-5 years in teaching mathematics in grade 7, and seven (7) attended 1-3 training sessions on DAMATH games in mathematics teaching.

This implies that mathematics teachers are in the thirty-six and forty age brackets. A study conducted by Aloka and Bojuwoye (2013) found older teachers, having had many years of teaching experience, are more mature, and more cautious than younger teachers when handling students' disciplinary problems. Many young teachers may feel overwhelmed and may not feel adequately supported in their roles, leading to a high turnover rate. On the other hand, older teachers may have developed more resilience and coping strategies to manage the challenges of teaching. According to Zafer and Aslihan (2012), older teachers are more effective in teaching and good in classroom management skills than younger teachers in high school. Moreover, female teachers dominated the teaching profession. Based on the study conducted by Ullah (2016), he asserted that there has been an ideological link between women's domestic role and their career as schoolteacher. Taking care of younger children in school is traditionally seen as an "extension of motherhood" and therefore considered a "natural" job for women. It is also seen that to effectively teach mathematics, the years of teaching play a very important role in delivering lessons to their students as it implies that the more experienced the teachers had gone through, the more knowledge she/he can share. Furthermore, one should have relevant training, or seminars attended in mathematics teaching by the teachers are also important for their part as a mathematics teacher. According to Mohd Ismail et al. (2018), literature reflected the disparity between teachers' age, experience, and teacher effectiveness. This phenomenon suggests that teachers' age and experience should be examined to determine the differences in relation to teacher effectiveness in delivering Higher Order Thinking Skills teaching. As the result implies that the teacher's skills got enhanced and developed because they attended various seminars.

Teachers' profile is a very important variable in this study as it helps to give us the idea of whether their teaching styles and the extent of use of the DAMATH Board Game is affected by their profile. Teachers' age, teaching experience, seminars attended, and years of experience significantly influenced their effectiveness in delivering quality education to students in the field of mathematics by integrating DAMATH board games in teaching mathematics.

Table 2. Profile of the Junior High School Teachers

Profile		f	%
Age	21-25 years old	1	14.3
	26-30 years old	0	0.0
	31-35 years old	0	0.0
	36-40 years old	4	57.1
	41-45 years old	1	14.3
	46 years old and above	1	14.3
Sex	Male	0	0.0
	Female	7	100.0
Civil Status	Single	3	42.9
	Married	4	57.1
Length of Service	1-5 years	2	28.6

in Teaching	6-10 years	2	28.6
	11-15 years	1	14.3
	over 15 years	2	28.6
Number of Years in Teaching Mathematics in Grade 7	1-5 years	5	71.4
	6-10 years	2	28.6
Relevant training/seminars/workshops on DAMATH games in mathematics teaching	1-3 trainings	7	100.0
	4-6 trainings	0	0.0
	7-9 trainings	0	0.0
	more than 9 trainings	0	0.0

Teaching Style of the Mathematics Teachers

Table 3 shows the teaching style of mathematics teachers perceived by the teachers itself. The table depicts the different perceptions of the teacher that were rated by them as Always Applied, Moderately Applied, Rarely Applied, and Never Applied. From the survey, it was revealed that conceptual understanding of the core knowledge gained an aggregate mean of 3.43 from teachers respectively which is interpreted as Always Applied, procedural fluency got 3.48 or interpreted as Always Applied, adaptive reasoning got 3.50 which is interpreted as Always Applied, productive disposition got 3.58 which is interpreted as Always applied, presence got 3.64 which is interpreted as Always Applied.

Table 3. Application of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics

Indicator	Teacher's Perception			
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	
Conceptual understanding of the core knowledge	Create meaningful and relevant lesson plans that build on core concepts.	3.57	0.53	Always Applied
	Encourage collaboration and discussion among teachers.	3.29	0.76	Always Applied
	Attend professional development and training.	3.43	0.53	Always Applied
	Use real world examples to demonstrate core concept	3.43	0.79	Always Applied
	Aggregate Mean	3.43	0.31	Always Applied
Procedural Fluency	Carry out procedures flexibly.	3.43	0.53	Always Applied
	Accurately follow procedures.	3.43	0.53	Always Applied
	Know when and how to use procedures appropriately	3.57	0.53	Always Applied
	Aggregate Mean	3.48	0.50	Always Applied
Adaptive reasoning	Encourage critical thinking and problem solving.	3.71	0.49	Always Applied
	Provide opportunities for collaborative learning and feedback.	3.43	0.79	Always Applied
	Use case studies and real - world examples.	3.29	0.49	Always Applied
	Encourage experimentation	3.57	0.53	Always Applied
Aggregate Mean	3.50	0.29	Always Applied	
Productive disposition	Provide opportunities for students' choice.	3.57	0.79	Always Applied
	Encourage students to take risk.	3.43	0.53	Always Applied
	Foster a growth mindset	3.57	0.53	Always Applied
	Aggregate Mean	3.52	0.42	Always Applied
Presence	Share of relevant professional experiences	3.71	0.76	Always Applied
	Set clear expectations and boundaries.	3.71	0.49	Always Applied
	Engage students in active learning.	3.71	0.76	Always Applied
	Establish personal connection with students.	3.57	0.53	Always Applied
	Use inclusive language and gestures.	3.71	0.49	Always Applied
	Being physically and emotionally present	3.43	0.79	Always Applied
Aggregate Mean	3.64	0.34	Always Applied	
Overall Mean	3.53	0.23	Always Applied	

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Never Applied); 1.76-2.50 (Rarely Applied), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Applied); 3.26-4.00 (Always Applied)

The above results imply that teachers have a conceptual understanding of the core knowledge in teaching mathematics. They create meaningful and relevant lesson plans based on their core concepts. So, teachers considered using real-world examples since real-world situations are associated with designing a conceptual understanding of the topic. Additionally, teachers encourage collaboration and discussion among their co-teachers to gather relevant ideas. Moreover, attending professional development and training is crucial for the teacher's efficacy in teaching. Furthermore, the procedural fluency statement signifies that teachers carry out the procedures flexibly and accurately. Also, teachers know when and how to use procedures appropriately. This means teachers should follow the procedures, have the knowledge of them, and be well-equipped with the skills to perform them more flexibly, accurately, and efficiently. In addition, adaptive reasoning provides opportunities for collaborative learning and feedback. It encourages critical thinking and problem-solving in teaching mathematics. Applying case studies and real-world examples in teaching delivers the most relevant and meaningful activities to enhance their reasoning skills. Moreover, a productive disposition fosters students' mindset, provides them with opportunities according to their preferences, and encourages taking risks in crucial situations, especially in real-world situations. Allowing students to choose and balance every circumstance prepared them for their roles in the community. Furthermore, the statement

presence shows that engaging students in active learning has the highest weighted mean. This implies showing relevant professionalism during instruction sets more explicit boundaries between the students and teachers. Establishing a personal connection with your students leads to engaging classroom instruction. Being physically and emotionally present is another way to know and interact well with every learner. Additionally, using inclusive language and gestures makes it easier for the students to comprehend the lesson well.

Teaching styles play a vital role in the teaching-learning process of the students. The teachers in mathematics must have these lists of teaching styles to give discussions effectively to students. Students can understand and gain more ideas about a specific topic through these teaching styles. Mathematical proficiency is not a one-dimensional trait and cannot be achieved by focusing on just one or two of these skills.

Extent Use of DAMATH Board Game

Table 4 shows the different perceptions of teachers regarding the extent of usage of DAMATH board games in terms of using real-world examples to connect the DAMATH game to mathematical concepts, provide clear instruction and expectations for the DAMATH game, and encourage reflection and analysis of the DAMATH game after playing.

Table 4. Use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics

Use of DAMATH in Teaching	Teacher's Perception		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Use real-world examples to connect the DAMATH game to mathematical concepts.	3.43	0.53	Always Applied
Provide clear instruction and expectations for the DAMATH game.	3.71	0.49	Always Applied
Encourage reflection and analysis of the DAMATH game after playing.	3.71	0.49	Always Applied
Overall	3.62	0.36	Always Applied

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Never Applied); 1.76-2.50 (Rarely Applied), 2.51-3.25 (Moderately Applied); 3.26-4.00 (Always Applied)

The above result implies that using DAMATH in teaching is designed to teach mathematical concepts. As such, the instructions and criteria for the game must be clear and simple to comprehend. It is essential that the teachers set clear instructions and expectations to enhance learning outcomes. As defined by De Freitas et al. (2018), educational gaming is "the use of games in educational contexts to achieve educational objectives." It is a pedagogical method that combines traditional and digital games to promote and enhance learning, teaching, and evaluation. In the classroom, board games are frequently used (Noda et al., 2019). As we recover from this pandemic and go in new directions, education may reinvent itself and offer better learning environments through its teaching techniques. It can also be involved through games, encouraging creative abilities. The missing component in our toolkit functions like a board game, substituting traditional lectures for a more participatory teaching approach. Beyond enhancing understanding, board games are excellent for reaching goals. It can be an enjoyable and motivating approach to learning while encouraging teamwork, challenge, and fun. (Charlier & De Fraigne, 2013). It boosts students' academic aptitude and cognitive ability, which leads to higher academic accomplishment (Byun & Loh, 2015). Game-based learning allows Students to study more actively and enthusiastically (Hilliard & Kargbo, 2017). According to the study by Lane et al. (2022), it prepares students for future learning by imparting new knowledge and skills, practicing, reinforcing previously acquired knowledge and skills, and developing 21st-century skills. Finally, the DAMATH game can also be used to illustrate real-life situations to help students better understand mathematical concepts.

The extent of use of DAMATH board games was determined by answering the survey questionnaire, and the results clearly show what things each teacher needs to consider in integrating DAMATH into teaching mathematics. Teachers' perception of the extent of use of DAMATH board games was also determined.

Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of Students

Table 5 shows the pre-test and post-test performance of the students in integers using DAMATH in terms of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. From the survey, it was revealed that the pre-test got a mean score of 5.21 which was interpreted as Developing and the post-test score got a mean score of 7.10 which was interpreted as Approaching Proficiency.

Table 5. Pre-Test and Post-Test Performance of Grade 7 students

Four Basic Mathematical Operations	Pre-Test				Post-Test			
	Mean	SD	Mean Grade	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Mean Grade	Interpretation
Addition	4.77	2.01	71	Beginning	6.43	2.01	77	Developing
Subtraction	3.8	2.04	69	Beginning	6.03	2.36	75	Developing
Multiplication	6.43	2.57	77	Developing	8.10	2.29	88	Proficient
Division	5.83	3.02	74	Beginning	7.83	2.11	86	Proficient
Overall	5.21	2.62	73	Beginning	7.10	2.35	81	Approaching Proficiency

Legend: 74-below (Beginning), 75-79 (Developing), 80-84 (Approaching Proficiency), 85-89 (Proficient), 90-100 (Advanced)

The DAMATH integration data demonstrates that after the program, students perform well on pre-test and post-test, including the four basic mathematical operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. The post-test mean scores are greater than the pre-test mean scores in all four operations. The total mean score demonstrates the program's positive effects on the student's performance. This information suggests that the DAMATH integration curriculum successfully strengthens students' mathematical abilities, especially in the four fundamental operations. It also emphasizes how crucial it is to use game-based methods like DAMATH while instructing and learning mathematics. According to the study of Alam et al. (2019), the pre-test/post-test model was significantly more effective in helping students achieve the learning outcomes in a lecture than the post-test-only model. Additionally, a study supported by Khan and Hassan (2018) investigated pre-tests' effect on learning mathematical concepts among secondary school students in Pakistan. The study found that pre-tests significantly improved student learning and understanding of mathematical concepts. Therefore, pre-tests and post-tests positively impact students achieving the expected learning outcome.

Application and Use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics

Table 6 shows the significant relationship between Application and Use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics. It was revealed that there is a significant relationship between application and use of DAMATH in teaching Mathematics.

Table 6. Significant Relationship between the application and use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics

Variables	Significance Level	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Application and Use of DAMATH in Teaching Mathematics	0.05	0.935	0.002	Reject H_0	Significant

*Level of significance at 0.05, Reject H_0 when p-value is less than the level of significance, Significant when H_0 is rejected.

Teachers applying DAMATH were found to be statistically significant in using DAMATH in teaching Mathematics. The result of the study indicates that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. This implies that applying a DAMATH board game in teaching mathematics is key to improving the use of DAMATH in teaching mathematics. It implies that he/she managed to consider the following terms: Use real-world examples to connect the DAMATH game to mathematical concepts, provide clear instruction and expectations for the DAMATH game, and encourage reflection and analysis of the DAMATH game after playing with the consideration of Conceptual Understanding of the Core Conceptual, Procedural Fluency, Adaptive Reasoning, Productive Disposition, and Presence. According to the study by Ortiz et al. (2022), gamification techniques were very effective in motivating learning; the serious game had a good user experience, and the students were satisfied with the learning experience. Thus, Grade 7 mathematics teachers consistently applied the concepts of mathematics in the application of the DAMATH board game in classroom instruction.

Pre-test and post-test performance in integers using DAMATH

Table 7 shows the significant difference between pre-test and post-test performance in integers using DAMATH on all basic Mathematical operations (Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication, and Division). The difference between Pre-test and Post-test performance of students in integers using DAMATH on all basic Mathematical operations was revealed to be significant.

Table 7. Significant difference of pre-test and post-test

Variables	Source of Difference	Mean	Standard Deviation	Test Value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pre-test Post-test	Addition	4.77 6.43	2.01 2.01	0.98	0.001	Reject H_0	Significant
Pre-test Post-test	Subtraction	3.8 6.03	2.04 2.36	0.941	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
Pre-test Post-test	Multiplication	6.43 8.10	2.57 2.29	0.881	0.005	Reject H_0	Significant
Pre-test Post-test	Division	5.83 7.83	3.02 2.11	0.912	0.001	Reject H_0	Significant

*Level of significance at 0.05, Reject H_0 when p-value is less than the level of significance, Significant when H_0 is rejected.

Students' performance on the pre-test and post-test in integers was found to have a significant difference in the extent of using DAMATH board games in teaching. The result of the study indicates that there is a significant difference between the two variables. It implies that the student's performance on the pre-test and post-test shows different levels of development or mastery of mathematical concepts and abilities, which may be seen in the pre-test and post-test results of the grade 7 students. The students can practice and apply what they have learned while playing the DAMATH integration game, and the post-test may reveal higher levels of achievement or mastery. DAMATH integration can provide valuable insights into the extent to which the game is an intervention to improve mathematical skills and critical thinking. This pre-test and post-test can show the differences in knowledge and skills before and after playing the game, providing evidence of the benefits of gamification in math education. A study supported by De Freitas et al. (2018) defines educational gaming as "the use of games in educational contexts to achieve educational objectives." It boosts students' academic aptitude and cognitive ability, which leads to higher academic accomplishment (Byun & Loh, 2015). Game-based learning allows Students to study more actively and enthusiastically (Hilliard & Kargbo, 2017). This suggests that DAMATH can be an effective

strategy for improving students' mathematical skills. This finding is essential for educators and policymakers looking for effective teaching strategies that can improve student's performance in mathematics. Therefore, applying DAMATH board games in teaching leads to a more positive attitude toward mathematics and improved academic performance.

Conclusion

Integrating the DAMATH board game into mathematics instruction has a significant impact on the teaching and learning processes of both teachers and students. A student's age, gender, and combined family income are some of the factors that affect their attentiveness to class discussion and their studies. Students' profiles are essential for the learning process because they help the education department plan school policies and teaching strategies to improve the learning process further. Moreover, the teacher's profile, which includes age, gender, civil status, length of service in teaching, number of years in teaching Grade 7 in Mathematics, and relevant training/workshops/seminars on DAMATH games in mathematics teaching, were also considered as influencing factors of the extent of usage of their teaching styles in using DAMATH Board games in teaching mathematics to students.

Mathematics teachers must possess teaching skills that could help them improve their teaching of mathematics lessons to students, such as conceptual understanding of the core knowledge, procedural fluency, adaptive reasoning, productive disposition, and presence. These five teaching styles bring quality education to students in terms of mathematics, and these should work together to create a significant teaching-learning experience between the students and teachers. As such, applying board games such as DAMATH in teaching mathematics demonstrates a positive effect on the student's performance. The use of manipulatives and game-like activities in DAMATH hugely contributed to the student's motivation and engagement, which in turn led to a better understanding of the concepts. Students' performance on the pre-test and post-test in integers had a significant difference in the use of DaMath board games in teaching. Results show different levels of development or mastery of mathematical concepts and abilities, which lead to a more positive attitude towards mathematics and improved academic performance. Thus, teachers should consider DaMath as another tool to better strengthen the students' mathematical abilities, especially in the four fundamental operations.

School stakeholders must be oriented by their problems in attaining an optimal teaching-learning process. They must embrace the benefits of implementing game-based learning or gamification as their new and innovative way of learning. The researchers proposed a program named AIMED or Advancing Integration thru a Multidimensional Educational approach in DAMATH. This program will integrate the use of the DAMATH board game in the classroom to address issues such as math anxiety, gaps in cognitive skills brought by a shift in learning modality, and ineffective teaching methods. DAMATH board games will enhance students' mathematical problem-solving strategies and skills, boost self-esteem in solving mathematical problems, and improve overall academic performance. DAMATH board game provides enjoyable and interactive learning for students and flexibility for teachers to implement new teaching styles that involve a more learner-centered approach in Mathematics.

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